

Evaluating Data-Driven Algorithm Portfolio Construction Methods at Scale Supplementary Material

1 Methodology

Table 1: Average number of unique best algorithms per function for different selection methods using per instance selection averaged over 24 functions with 5 instances.

Method	Avg. unique best algs per function
GREEDY	2.70 (0.98)
HEURISTIC	2.67 (0.94)
EA SO	2.62 (1.00)
COS DS	2.65 (1.01)
COS MIS	2.61 (1.05)
EUC DS	2.34 (1.05)
EUC MIS	2.25 (1.03)
PEAR DS	1.80 (0.92)
PEAR MIS	1.97 (0.96)
SPEAR DS	1.83 (0.96)
SPEAR MIS	1.84 (0.92)

1.1 Greedy constructive *heuristic* approach

The objective of this portfolio selection method:

Candidate algorithms $[1, 2, \dots, m] \in \mathcal{I}$

Portfolio set $\mathcal{S} \subset \mathcal{I}$, where \mathcal{I} is a finite set containing all algorithm configurations.

Set-function F

$$F : 2^{\mathcal{I}} \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}, \mathcal{S} \mapsto F(\mathcal{S})$$

Where F is to maximise performance for each function/instance: let the mean performance of algorithm j in function/instance k be defined as

$$\mu_{k,j} = \frac{1}{|I_{k,j}|} \sum_{i \in I_{k,j}} x_{ij},$$

where $I_{k,j}$ is the set of indices i in function/instance k for which x_{ij} is available. Then

$$F = \sum_{k=1}^N \max_j \mu_{k,j},$$

where N is the number of functions/instances.

So the objective is formulated as

$$\max_{\mathcal{S} \subset \mathcal{I}, |\mathcal{S}|=n} F(\mathcal{S}).$$

1.2 Single-objective evolutionary portfolio selection

Portfolio redundancy mitigation constraint For each function (or instance) k , a ‘win’ is awarded to the algorithm with the highest mean performance, defined as:

$$w_j = \sum_{k=1}^N \mathbf{1}\left\{j = \arg \max_{1 \leq i \leq n} \mu_{k,i}\right\},$$

as the number of wins for algorithm j , where $\mathbf{1}\{\cdot\}$ is the indicator function. If

$$K_{\text{wins}} = \sum_j \mathbf{1}\{w_j > 0\},$$

is the number of algorithms that win at least once, this should be equal to n .

Table 2: Evolutionary operators used in the single- and multi-objective algorithms. Algorithms were implemented using pymoo^[1].

Operator	Single-objective (GA)	Multi-objective (NSGA-II)
Initialisation	Random portfolios of size \mathbf{n} generated by sampling distinct algorithm indices without replacement.	Same as single-objective.
Selection	Internal parent selection of GA, guided by minimisation of f_1 .	Internal parent selection of NSGA2, guided by non-dominated ranking and diversity over f_1 and f_2 .
Crossover	UniformCrossover : each gene is inherited from either parent with probability 0.5; duplicates are repaired using unused parental or global indices.	Same as single-objective.
Mutation	IntegerSwapMutation : either replace zero-win algorithms with unselected ones, or swap one selected algorithm with one unselected algorithm.	Same as single-objective.
Replacement	Built-in GA survivor selection based on fitness; duplicates eliminated.	Built-in NSGA2 environmental selection using non-dominated sorting and crowding distance; duplicates eliminated.
Termination	Fixed generation budget.	Fixed generation budget.

Table 3: Tuned evolutionary algorithm parameters

Dataset	Setting	Mut. Repair	Mut.	Cross.	Pop./Gen.
CMA	Per-instance (5, 30)	0.0608	0.3216	0.4444	98 / 99
	Per-function (5, 30)	0.0351	0.4110	0.4021	100 / 97
DE	Per-instance (5, 30)	0.1172	0.4409	0.7399	66 / 81
	Per-function (5, 30)	0.0769	0.5847	0.4418	77 / 91

2 Results

Multi-objective portfolio selection from Pareto front: As described in the main paper, for the multi-objective EAs, oracle selection was used to select the portfolio from the produced solution set. Figure 1 shows the performance of portfolios selected using different methods. When selecting entirely based on the second objective (O2), which aims to generalise the portfolios, the overall performance is lower in all settings. The portfolio performances are similar when they are selected based on the first objective (O1) or with the oracle selection method. This pattern only breaks in the CMA 30d setting, where the oracle selection method performs better.

Figure 1: Comparison of different solution selection methods for multi-objective portfolio selection on the leave-function-out scenario.

References

- [1] J. Blank and K. Deb. pymoo: Multi-objective optimization in python. *IEEE Access*, 8:89497–89509, 2020.